

D2.1: SotA, requirements, initiatives

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Responsible author	Erik Cornelisse (TNO)		
Additional authors and contributors	Simon Dalmolen (TNO), Andreas El Saer (INLE), Kata Trifkovic (INLE), Anna Twarogowska (ILVO)		
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Glossary of terms and acronyms used

Acronym / Term	Description
API	Application Programming Interface
CMM	Capability Maturity Model (see section 2.3)
Dataspace	A decentralized infrastructure for trustworthy data sharing and exchange in data ecosystems based on commonly agreed principles. (see section 2.1)
DID	Decentralized Identifiers (see section 2.2)
EIF	European Interoperability Framework (see section 2.2)
Federated	Decentralized self-governing entities collaborating with each other to achieve a common objective based on common policies, controls and enforcement abilities governing the use of shared resources and data in particular among participants. (see section 2.2)
FLW	Food Loss and Waste
GUI	Graphical User Interface
IDS	International Data Spaces (See 2.1)
IDSA	International Data Spaces Association
IDS-RAM	International Data Spaces – Reference Architecture Model
Interoperability	Interoperability is the ability of organisations to interact towards mutually beneficial goals, involving the sharing of information and knowledge between these organisations, through the business processes they support, by means of the exchange of data between their ICT systems. (See section 2.1)
Participant	A legal entity with a unique verifiable identity, authenticated and accepted within a dataspace, who has accepted and is committed to the governance model of that dataspace. (See section 2.4)
SILL	Systemic Innovations Living Labs
SML	Solution Maturity Model (see section 2.3)
SSI	Self-sovereign Identities (see section 2.2)
TRL	Technology Readiness Level (see section 2.3)
ZeroW	Zero Waste project
OFLW	Zero Food Lose Waste

Table 1 Glossary of terms and acronyms used

Executive summary

The goal of this document is to describe an architectural starting point for the implementation of a managed European Zero Food Loss Waste (OFLW) dataspace based on previous dataspace initiatives and standards.

“A dataspace is a decentralized infrastructure for trustworthy data sharing and exchange in data ecosystems based on commonly agreed principles” [3]

The new European Interoperability Framework[2], OpenDEI[3] and the International Data Space (IDS) reference architecture model[4] are used as the *architectural foundation* for the integration of different data sources and services in a decoupled and modular way and to ensure data sovereignty with a dataspace.

Other dataspace initiatives and IT standards are investigated to determine the maturity level of solutions for the required building blocks in the current and upcoming technology - and data landscape. A *Solution Maturity Model* has been defined and used to indicate the readiness of the available solutions from these initiatives for a OFLW dataspace.

This document describes a comprehensive overview of:

- the *generic types of roles / actors* required for the description of high level requirements with use of functional scenario's (use-case);
- the *high level requirements / use-cases* for a dataspace in general c.q. not specific for the ZeroW Systemic Innovations Living Lab (SILL);
- the *high level requirements* for a dataspace governance model;
- the *current available solutions* for implementing a OFLW dataspace as result of the state of the art analysis;
- *recommendations* for further research & development topics within ZeroW.

A comprehensive and combined overview of required actors and high level requirements for dataspaces and corresponding governance model has been constructed by work package 2 - task T2.1 because they are not available from other initiatives.

The main conclusion is that there are mature enough solutions to setup a minimal viable dataspace as starting point for sharing data within and across the SILLs in a trusted and secure manner. More research and development is required and addressed within the ZeroW project for defining a common vocabulary, API's, federated catalogue/ marketplace and a governance model for the OFLW dataspace.

1. Introduction

ZeroW project summary

ZeroW aims at reducing Food Loss and Waste by employing systemic innovations, to halve by 2030 and to near-zero by 2050. This systemic innovation approach is based on the development of a core demonstrative environment supporting nine Systemic Innovation Living Labs (SILLs) along the value chain, complemented by assessment activities to ensure a long term environmental and economic sustainability of zero-FLW (0FLW) solutions and a just transition towards a near-zero FLW system.

Figure 1 ZeroW at a glance

The ZeroW approach involves the following elements:

Figure 2 ZeroW approach

To achieve the ZeroW goals, the project is divided into eleven work-packages with more specific objectives, tasks and deliverables.

Figure 3 WP2 tasks, deliverables, objectives

Mapping ZeroW outputs

Purpose of this chapter is to map ZeroW Grant Agreement commitments, both within the formal Deliverable and Task description, against the current document.

ZEROW GA Component Title	ZEROW GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
DELIVERABLE			
D2.1 SotA, requirements, initiatives	<i>"SotA, requirements, initiatives ". Source [1]</i>	Chapter 2	Analyses the initiatives taken in account and covers the state of the art analysis with use of the building blocks as proposed by the OpenDEI initiative [3].
		Chapter 3	Specifies the generic c.q. SILL independent requirements for a OFLW dataspace.
		Chapter 4	Contains conclusions as result of the state of the art analysis, inventory of the requirements and recommendations for other workpackages and deliverables.

TASKS		
<p>T2.1 Design and definition of the OFLW Data Space</p>	<p><i>“The initial subtask is to relate to initiatives (DIH, GAIA-X, BDVA, IDS(A), DEMETER, FENIX) in the current and future data and technology landscape for OFLW”. Source [1]</i></p>	<p>Chapter 2</p> <p>The following initiatives are investigated: EIF, OpenDEI, SmartAgriHubs DIH, GAIA-X, BDVA, IDS(A), FIWARE, DSBA, DEMETER, FENIX, NIST CFRA, eIDAS, Ploutos.</p>
	<p><i>“The task will start and accelerate the development of a common data space enabling the integration of different data sources and services in a decoupled and modular way, ensuring data sovereignty. Data sharing in a federated data sharing environment can be characterised as a system-of-systems, in which a multitude of dedicated systems pool their resources and capabilities together to create a new, overarching, system with value adding functionality and performance”. Source [1]</i></p>	<p>Chapter 3</p> <p>Requirements are identified from previous initiatives for the technology building blocks but also for the governances aspects of a OFLW dataspace. New requirements have been derived to support a federation of services.</p>
	<p><i>“This task will take the International Data Space (IDS) reference model as a starting point, providing method and tools for its implementation and promoting the adoption among federation members. This adoption includes the deployment of IDS-based connectors and essential components, and the participation of a Certification Authority and a Dynamic Attribute Provisioning Service to ensure secure exchanges among certified participants. The IDSA reference architecture is at the basis of this Task and particularly its DIN SPEC 27070 pre-standard”. Source [1]</i></p>	<p>Chapter 3</p> <p>The International Data Space (IDS) Reference Architecture Model (IDS-RAM) is used as a starting point for the generic requirements for the OFLW dataspace.</p> <p>Solutions based on IDS-RAM have been evaluated with use of a Solution Maturity model to get an indication which functionality requires more research and development to implement a OFLW dataspace.</p>

Table 2 Deliverable and work description (Source [1])

Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

Approach

The new European Interoperability Framework[2], OpenDEI[3] and the International Data Space (IDS) reference architecture model[5] are used as the *architectural foundation* for the integration of different data sources and services in a decoupled and modular way and to ensure data sovereignty with a dataspace. Other dataspace initiatives and IT standards are also investigated to determine the maturity level of solutions for the required “building blocks” as defined by the OpenDEI[3] initiative. A *Solution Maturity Model* has been defined in section 2.3 and is used to indicate the readiness of the available solutions from these initiatives for a OFLW dataspace. From the analysis of previous initiatives a combined and comprehensive overview is created for required roles and actors, high level requirements for the technology and governance aspects. Based on that overview, missing requirements have been identified and completed with proposed requirements. All requirements have a reference to the source for justification, traceability and reviewing purposes.

Document structure

Chapter 1 – *Introduction* describing the objectives, context and the approach for this document;

Chapter 2 – *State of the Art analysis* of previous initiatives based on a common unit: Solution Maturity levels. Also a common set of roles and actors have been identified required for describing the functional use-cases (scenario's);

Chapter 3 – *Requirements* at a high-level for a generic implementation of a dataspace, have been collected from previous initiatives. A proposal for missing requirements is included to get a complete overview;

Chapter 4 – *Conclusions and recommendations* about the availability of solutions and required research & development topics for the implementation of a OFLW dataspace.

The high-level requirements and the governance requirements in particular can be used for the implementation of OFLW dataspace and the development of collaborative business and governance models for data sharing in OFLW.

2. State of the Art analysis

2.1 Dataspace foundation

A common starting point for the design of dataspaces is based on three European initiatives: the new European Interoperability Framework[2], OpenDEI[3] and IDSA[4]. A dataspace is an architectural concept for sharing data and defined as:

A dataspace is a decentralized infrastructure for trustworthy data sharing and exchange in data ecosystems based on commonly agreed principles¹.

Source: OpenDEI [3]

The initial objective of a dataspace is to remain in control of the data and the infrastructure required for the exchange of information, also known as *data - and digital sovereignty*². This explains the “decentralized” part in the definition above.

Furthermore it is a collaboration or cooperation of organisations to reduce the costs for implementing a secure mechanism for trustworthy data sharing by (re)using IT services under commonly agreed rules and principles. Developing and deploying IT services once and share them with many, not only reduces the costs but also allows new participants to join faster and without having specialised knowledge of deploying such services of their own. A dataspace is in the first place an organisation of companies who join forces to achieve a mutual objective and in the second place it consists of enabling IT services for data-exchange and is not intended for data storage in contrast to a data lake or database.

¹ This definition implies that the scope of a dataspace is based on common ground of the participants of that dataspace. As result multiple dataspaces will exist and some form of collaboration between them will be required as well.

² **Digital sovereignty** refers to the ability of a nation, government, or organization to maintain control over its digital infrastructure, data, and online activities. This includes the ability to set and enforce rules and regulations for the use of digital technologies within its borders, as well as the ability to protect its digital assets from external threats such as cyber-attacks. Digital sovereignty also includes the ability to develop and maintain a domestic digital industry, including the production and use of digital technologies and services.

Data sovereignty, on the other hand, refers to the concept that individuals and organizations have the right to control the collection, use, and dissemination of their personal data. It is the principle that individuals have the right to decide how their data is collected, used, and shared, and that they have the right to access and correct their data. In practice, data sovereignty means that individuals and organizations have control over the personal data that they generate and share, and that they can make decisions about how that data is used. This concept is particularly important in the context of the internet and digital technologies, where personal data is often collected, used, and shared in ways that may not be immediately transparent to the individual or organization generating the data.

While both concepts are related, they focus on different levels of control and decision-making. Digital sovereignty refers to the ability of a nation or organization to control and regulate its digital infrastructure and activities, while data sovereignty refers to the right of individuals and organizations to control their personal data. Both concepts are important in the digital age, as they help to ensure that individuals and organizations can make informed decisions about their digital activities and protect their digital assets.

New European Interoperability Framework (EIF)

Ref 2 The EIF initiative provides guidance, through a set of recommendations on how to improve governance of interoperability activities. The interoperability governance model is the most known part of this framework and is useful to breakdown the scope into smaller aspects to be considered when implementing a dataspace.

Figure 4 Interoperability governance model

The European Interoperability Framework is a commonly accepted starting point for defining dataspace specific governance models.

Interoperability is defined as:

Interoperability is the ability of organisations to interact towards mutually beneficial goals, involving the sharing of information and knowledge between these organisations, through the business processes they support, by means of the exchange of data between their ICT systems.

Source: European Interoperability Framework [2]

OpenDEI Position Paper: Design Principles for Data Spaces

Ref 3

The OpenDEI Position Paper - Design Principles for Data Spaces[3] describes the fundamentals of dataspace and uses a functional breakdown based on twelve building blocks. These building blocks enable business, operational, organisational and technical capabilities of dataspace.

Figure 5 Building blocks (source [3])

These building blocks and the description are used:

- as starting point for dataspace requirements,
- to analyse a specific implementation of a dataspace or
- to support (strategic) business analyses.

The Position Paper[3] contains an overview of all aspects to consider and is compliant and complementary to the European Interoperability Framework[2].

International Data Space - Reference Architecture Model (IDS-RAM)

Ref 4 The International Data Spaces Association (IDSA) provides a reference architecture model based on standards and technologies. It also provides governance models to facilitate secure and standardized data exchange and data linkage in a trusted business ecosystem.

The IDS Reference Architecture Model[4] is compliant with the European Interoperability Framework[2] and the Position Paper[3] and provides guidelines for a technical implementation: also known as the “IDS connectors”.

Figure 6 IDS – Reference Architecture Model (source [4])

The IDS-RAM identified the following software components / IT-services³:

- *Security Gateway: IDS Connector;*
- *Broker;*
- *Identity provider: Dynamic Attribute Provisioning Service (DAPS);*
- *Vocabulary hub;*
- *Clearing house*
- *App store.*

The IDS-RAM[4] and DIN-SPEC-270290[5] were chosen as starting point in the Grant Agreement[1] because “working” solutions are available for the technical implementation of a 0FLW dataspace.

³ See for a detailed description reference [4] and [5].

The following figure visualizes the position of this document in relation to other initiatives and the IDS-RAM and DIN specifications in particular.

Figure 7 Document relations of D2.1 with other project & initiatives

This document D2.1 – SotA, requirements, initiatives uses the functional parts of the IDS-Reference architecture model and the DIN-27070 specifications to create a comprehensive overview completed with information from other projects and initiatives to fill the gaps c.q. missing parts. The technical requirements from IDS-RAM and DIN-27070 in particular will be used as foundation for deliverable D2.2 - the specification of the required OFLW dataspace connectors. (ZeroW partners: TNO) Working implementations of the following IDS compliant software components are available from Fraunhofer Institute and TNO with Solution Maturity level 3:

- *Security Gateway;*
- *(Federated) Broker;*
- *DAPS;*
- *Vocabulary hub;*
- *Clearing house.*

These components are fully described [4][5] and available for the ZeroW project . Setting up these IDS components as IT-services will jump start the OFLW dataspace implementation and provide the following building block functionalities:

- *Identity management;*
- *Trusted Exchange;*
- *Access & Usage control/policies;*
- *Metadata & Discovery services.*

A technical framework and supporting tooling c.q. Vocabulary hub is also available for implementing the following functionalities:

- *Data models & Formats* (ZeroW & SILL specific);
- *Data exchange API*;

In IDS-RAM, a *Vocabulary hub* is identified as a generic supporting dataspace service. This can be implemented with use of existing tooling such as VoCoReg⁴ and Semantic Treehouse⁵ to enable a community driven approach where participants of a dataspace c.q. SILL participants can define and agree upon semantic models, message formats and supporting Application Programming Interfaces (API's).

The IDSA Rule book [6] defines processes, legal, organisational, functional and technical agreements for the implementation of a dataspace. A recent publication *Designing Data Spaces – The Ecosystem approach to competitive Advantage*[7], gives an overview of the economic and technological and aspects of dataspace, based on the Gaia-X and IDSA initiatives.

2.2 Other dataspace initiatives & standards

This section contains other dataspace related initiatives and standards which are analysed and used in this document. The selected initiatives are the result from a quick scan of projects known by ZeroW partners and filtered based on data sharing related technologies and dataspace in particular.

Reference to these initiatives and standards are marked on the left side of the page. This section does NOT describe nor summarizes the initiatives and standards but only elaborates on potential solutions useful for the ZeroW project and the design and realization of OFLW dataspace in particular.

The NIST Cloud Federation Reference Architecture (CFRA)

Ref 8

The National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) of the US department of Commerce has published in 2020 a paper about a cloud federation reference architecture (CFRA). The CFRA contains design patterns, requirements, guidelines and considerations which can be applied for the design of dataspace.

Several requirements in section 3 of this document are directly derived or inspired by recommendations from CFRA, especially regarding topics which are not or

⁴ VoCol - An Integrated Environment for Collaborative Vocabulary Development. VoCoReg is an VoCol version to work As A Service. See also <https://www.vocoreg.com/>

⁵ Semantic Treehouse is developed to enable the development of community driven API's. See also <https://www.semantic-treehouse.nl/>

moderately described in IDS-RAM[4]. The following definition for federated services has also been derived from this paper.

Federated services are decentralized self-governing entities collaborating with each other to achieve a common objective based on common policies, controls and enforcement abilities governing the use of shared resources and data in particular among participants.

Source: Derived from the definition by NIST[6]

Note Federated services are of interest of the ZeroW project because the need for a federated Catalogue⁶ is foreseen to enable participants to publish and discover: goods and services c.q. bringing supply and demand more and easier together.

electronic IDentification, Authentication and trust Services (eIDAS)

Ref 8 eIDAS is an EU regulation on electronic identification and trust services for electronic transactions to reduce trade barriers within the EU. It has created standards for identification and authentication which are important for a trustworthy dataspace. A proposal for a European Digital Identity framework toolbox is expected at the end of 2022 which might be useful for the ZeroW project because it provides a technical architecture and a reference framework of a unified European approach.

Self-sovereign identity (SSI)[22] and the use of Decentralized Identities (DID)[23] are also two topics of interest for ZeroW because of the expected multiple identities of the participants in the agriculture sector. However, a lot of research is still required and besides eIDAS also other initiatives such as GAIA-X have put these topics on their agenda. Medio 2022, there are no SSI and DID solutions for dataspace available yet, which are mature enough for the ZeroW project.

SmartAgriHubs - Digital Innovation Hubs (DIH)

Ref 10 SmartAgriHubs is a Horizon 2020 project initiated by Europe and brings together a consortium of well over 164 partners in the European agri-food sector. Digitization of the European agriculture is the main focus by providing digital solutions. In this project a DIH capability maturity model[11] has been developed. This model can also be used for the ZeroW project to assess the digital solutions developed and provided in other dataspace related initiatives and standards. In this State of the Art analysis, this capability maturity model will be used to determine the level of maturity of the twelve building blocks [3] in the upcoming section 2.3 of this document. (ZeroW partners: TNO)

⁶ A federated catalogue is a federated service to publish and discover meta-information about participants, services and information available within a (federation of) dataspace(s)

GAIA-X

Ref 12,13 Gaia-X is an European project to create a *federated* and secure data infrastructure based on the International Data Spaces (IDS) standard to enable transparent, open and self-determined exchange of data. Gaia-X promotes a federated register (also known as a federated catalogue) to store and share (meta) information about available data and services among the participants of dataspaces. A semantic standard for discovery of *self-description* of participants and (meta)data will be proposed medio 2022 by Gaia-X which might be useful as starting point for the development of a *federated catalogue* within the ZeroW project. Self-sovereign identities, Access control and Usage control are of interest as well, which are on the agenda of the Gaia-X Data Exchange working group. (ZeroW partners: TNO)

FIWARE

Ref 14 The FIWARE Foundation has developed an Open Source framework of platform components to accelerate the development of IT solutions for, among others, the AgriFood domain. Although the FIWARE solution doesn't use IDS compliant connectors, they already have an operational installed base of IT solutions to optimise the production in farms. This might be of interest for WP3 and the SILLs in particular in case there are additional applications and Internet of Things (IoT) solutions required.

Eclipse Dataspace Connector (EDC) & Catena-X

Ref 15 The Eclipse Dataspace Connector (EDC) is a software framework for sovereign, inter-organizational data exchange. Its objective is to integrate with existing identity, data catalogues, and transfer technologies to provide compliance, policy, and control capabilities across organizations and within different ecosystems.

The design goal is to create a modular software framework for connectors with well-defined API's where each connector can collaborate with other connectors in a federated but controlled and sovereign way.

Ref 16 Based on Gaia -X and the International Data Space Association (IDSA), Catena-X focusses in addition on *data throughput* and *control of sovereignty*. The Eclipse Dataspace Connector has gained a lot of attention caused by Catena-X but ... although the framework is built upon the concepts of Gaia-X and IDSA, it resulted in the development of new software modules. Currently there are no stable⁷ versions of these modules available (yet) and in the documentation is also under construction. The design objectives of the EDC are ambiguous and especially decentralised identities and sovereignty aspects are of interest. However, the

⁷ The software modules have passed all verifications / tests and the remaining bugs are considered as acceptable.

current implementations of EDC modules are less mature than the IDS connectors from Fraunhofer, Sovity and TNO. (ZeroW partners involved with Catena-X: TNO)

The Big Data Value Association (BDVA)

Ref 17 BDVA focuses on developing an Innovation Ecosystem[18] to enable (big) data and AI technologies in combination with data platforms and dataspace. However the dataspace technology is a different kind than IDS and is focused on a framework set of tools and methodology around Trustworthy and Industrial IA Engineering. For ZeroW the innovation ecosystem and the methodologies about trustworthiness are of interest.

Data Space Business Alliance (DSBA)

Ref 19 The Data Spaces Business Alliance is a joint initiative of the Gaia-X European Association for Data and Cloud AISBL, the FIWARE Foundation, the International Data Spaces Association (IDSA) and the Big Data Value Association (BDVA). Together they try to increase the adaptation of dataspace by alignment among the several initiatives of the common functional components such as identities, identity management and access control. This will result in changes in the IDS-Reference Architecture and potentially new standards. Therefore, the ZeroW project must monitor these developments and adapt accordingly to benefit too from a more accepted implementation standard for dataspace. (ZeroW partner TNO is involved)

FENIX Network

Ref 20 FENIX aims to develop the first European federated architecture for data sharing, serving the first European logistics community of shippers, logistics service providers, mobility infrastructure providers, cities, and authorities to offer interoperability between any individual existing and future platforms. ZeroW can:

1. learn from FENIX's ecosystem of Data and Services design and architecture;
2. take into consideration the federated network architecture of FENIX. the sharing of information (federated data catalogues) between the SILLs and, to ensure interoperability and common protocols for supporting these data sharing services; and
3. consider the FENIX connector during the design and the definition phase of ZeroW's Connector

Ref 21 Detailed information about the technical architecture can be found in the FENIX deliverable D3.1 the final version. (ZeroW Partners: INLE)

DEMETER (H2020-AI)

- Ref 25 Is a large-scale deployment of farmer centric interoperable smart farming-IoT based platforms delivered through pilots. Covers a wide spectrum of agricultural sub-sectors to demonstrate and evaluate how innovations and extended capabilities benefit from the interoperability mechanisms. ZeroW can learn from the way DEMETER delivers an Interoperability Space for the agri-food domain.
- Ref 26,27 DEMETER has defined an Reference architecture[26] which uses different protocols and API's than the IDS-Reference architecture model. However both architectures can be combined at a technical level with use of gateways and on a semantical level by using the DEMETER Agriculture Information Model (AIM) [27] as a common foundation. (ZeroW partners: WIT, F6S, ITC)

Internet of Food and Farm 2020 (H2020-IA)

- Ref 28 IoF2020 aims to accelerate IoT adoption for securing sufficient, safe and healthy food and to strengthen competitiveness of farming & food chains in Europe. It has a similar approach to ZeroW since technologies are demonstrated. ZeroW can learn from this approach to ensure a smooth link between the technological development WPs (WP2 & WP3) and the SILL realisation. (ZeroW partners: WUR, EV-ILVO, BIOS, ART21)

PLOUTOS (H2020-IA)

- Ref 29 PLOUTOS develops a Sustainable Innovation Framework that follows a systemic approach to the agri-food sector. It will deploy Sustainable Innovation Pilots, where using a Multi-Actor Approach new innovative solutions and methodologies will be implemented. It has common elements with ZeroW, so lessons from PLOUTOS can be translated to ZeroW with the focus on FLW reduction, and vice versa. Relevant innovations for ZeroW are:
- reduction of food waste (PLOUTOS - Sustainable Innovation Pilot 9);
 - a semi-integrated approach for the development of business models (WP3) and behavior change (WP2);
 - development of semantic models and data-sharing technologies (WP4);
 - a Sustainable Innovation Framework which can be used as source for inspiration for WP1 - "Systemic Innovation Assessment".
- (ZeroW partners: ITC, TNO)

Agricultural Interoperability and Analysis System - ATLAS (H2020-IA)

- Ref 30 ATLAS develops an open digital service platform as a sustainable ecosystem for innovative data-driven agriculture, to overcome interoperability problems. Like DEMETER, IoF2020 and PLOUTOS, ZeroW can learn from their experiences and although their architectures target connectivity between devices. With additional research and development effort, these IoT architectures can be connected as well to an IDS compliant dataspace.

2.3 Inventory of building block solutions

This section describes the maturity level for each of the twelve OpenDEI building blocks[2] based on the availability of solutions to implement them, in analogy with the capability maturity model(CMM), the technology readiness levels(TRLs) and the DIH maturity levels [11]. Solution maturity levels (SLM)⁸ are used to indicate which functionalities (building blocks) require more research and development and which ones are already suitable enough within a specific context c.q. ZeroW.

The following solution maturity levels for the functional building blocks are defined:

	Level	General characteristics of solution	Keywords
1	Ad-hoc	Only reactively offered upon demand.	<i>Initial: chaotic, very poor, initial, basic</i>
2	Low	Slightly structured, guidelines are available, an attributed task for someone in the project, partners have some experience in providing the solution.	<i>Repeatable: organised, defined, managed, poor, repeatable, accepted</i>
3	Intermediate	Structured and fully documented, there is at least one "trusted" organisation providing the solution as a business process.	<i>Defined: standardised, supported, defined, average</i>
4	High	Adopts and applies best practice, actively support from operational users.	<i>Managed: predictable, measured, mature, developed, systematical</i>
5	Excellent	Accepted as best practice and active contribution to other initiatives such as IDSA and Gaia-X.	<i>Optimized: innovation black belt, synergised, optimising, best practice, sustained</i>

Table 3 - Solution Maturity levels for building blocks

Example of a conclusion:

Building block	SML	Comments
Identity management	Intermediate	Multiple and different identities for the same participant need to be resolved which requires additional development effort.

This means that there are solutions available for "Identity management" which are fully described and can be provided as a business process by a trusted organisation within the ZeroW project but ...

additional development effort for ZeroW is foreseen to deal with the "agriculture reality" where growers and farmers can have multiple (different) identities depending on the participating business organisation.

⁸ CMM is a development model and relates to the degree of formality and optimization of processes. TRLs are a method for understanding the technical maturity of a technology. The solution maturity model is a mix of both and inspired by the DIH maturity levels which also assesses a mix of processes, services and technologies.

IDS compliant solutions

Working implementations of the following IDS compliant software components are available with Solution Maturity level 3 - Intermediate:

- *Security Gateway;*
- *(Federated) Broker;*
- *Dynamic Attribute Provisioning Service (DAPS);*
- *Vocabulary hub;*
- *Clearing house.*

These components are fully described [4][5] and available for the ZeroW project. Setting up these IDS components as IT-services will jump start the OFLW dataspace implementation and provide the following building block functionalities:

- *Identity management;*
- *Trusted Exchange;*
- *Access & Usage control/policies;*
- *Metadata & Discovery services.*

A technical framework and supporting tooling c.q. Vocabulary hub is also available for implementing the following functionalities:

- *Data models & Formats (ZeroW & SILL specific);*
- *Data exchange API;*

In IDS-RAM, a *Vocabulary hub* is identified as a generic supporting dataspace service. This can be implemented with use of existing tooling such as Semantic Treehouse⁹ to enable a community driven approach where participants of a dataspace c.q. SILL participants can define and agree upon semantic models, message formats and supporting Application Programming Interfaces (API's).

Data interoperability solutions

Data models & formats

[low]

A dataspace information model is available as starting point but SILL specific extensions are expected to support business operations. For defining a common terminology(semantics), the use of an IDS Vocabulary hub can support the creation and maintenance of community driven data models & formats.

⁹ Semantic Treehouse is developed to enable the development of community driven API's. See also <https://www.semantic-treehouse.nl/>

Data Exchange API

[low]

Templates and guidelines are available as a starting point but SILL specific implementations are expected to support business operations and the business specific data models in particular. For defining common interfaces, the use of an IDS Vocabulary hub can support the creation and maintenance of community driven API's.

Provenance & traceability

[intermediate]

Although a working solution is available, it is expected that this functionality is not required for a minimal implementation of a OFLW dataspace.

Data sovereignty solutions

Identity management

[intermediate]

A working and fully described solution can be provided with combined implementation of an IDS compliant Dynamic Attribute Provisioning Service (DAPS) and Security Gateway.

Trusted Exchange

[intermediate]

A working and fully described solution can be provided with an IDS compliant Security Gateway implementation.

Access & usage control/policies

[intermediate]

A working and fully described solution can be provided with an IDS compliant Security Gateway implementation.

Data value creation solutions

Metadata & discovery services

[intermediate]

A working and fully described solution can be provided with an IDS compliant Broker implementation.

Publication & Marketplace services

[ad-hoc]

Proof of concept implementations of IDS compliant Publication & Marketplace services are available. Research and development is on-going and expected to be based on the recent development of an IDS compliant federated broker.

Data usage accounting

[ad-hoc]

Although a proof of concept is available, it is expected that this functionality is not required for a minimal implementation of a OFLW dataspace..

Dataspace governance solutions

Business agreements

[low]

There are no ready to use business agreements or templates found specifically targeted for dataspace. However there are guidelines with topics to consider.

Operational agreements

[low]

There are no ready to use operational agreements or templates found specifically targeted for dataspace. However there are guidelines such as the IDSA Rule book [6] with topics to take in account.

Organisational agreements

[low]

are no ready to use organisational agreements or templates found specifically targeted for dataspace. However there are guidelines such as the IDSA Rule book[6] with topics to take in account.

Federated Dataspace solutions

Federation means in this context the collaboration among decentralized¹⁰ entities to achieve a common objective. In case of federated data-services it is about sharing information between distributed services where the information can be requested and handled at one service while the data itself can be stored distributed across one or more other federating services.

Note A federation of data-services can be implemented within a single dataspace or across (federating) dataspace but the governance models of each dataspace needs to be taken in account.

¹⁰ Decentralisation of data storage and IT-services in general is a mitigating measurement to increase more control for each participant and reduce a dominating influence by a single participant. In ultimo, keeping the data at the source will also make it easier to implement more control over the data: to achieve more data-sovereignty.

Federated Catalogue

[low]

A Federated Catalogue¹¹ will be developed in the ZeroW project which requires more research and development. Depending on the business requirements of the SILLs a federated catalogue will build upon a federated version of the following building blocks:

- *(Federated) Meta data & Discovery services [intermediary];*
- *(Federated) Publication & Marketplace services [ad-hoc].*

2.4 Inventory of actors and roles

This section provides a comprehensive overview of generic types of roles/actors for a dataspace which is currently not available from other initiatives. The terms role and actor are synonyms and the term actor will be used in this document.

Goal This section describes the generic types of actors required for the description of high level requirements with use of functional use-cases c.q scenario's. Since the naming as well as the definitions of these actors are not unified among the used references (such as [2][3][4][5][6][7][8]), this section gives a brief description for each actor to be used within the ZeroW project.

Generic type of actors

At a high level, three basic types of actors are distinguished: *natural persons*, *services* and a *group* of actors . An actor can act on behalf of its *self* or perform a (*delegated*) action on behalf of another actor which becomes relevant in case of legal issues.

¹¹ A federated Catalogue is a federated IT-service able to provide meta-information (descriptions) about participants, business and IT-services and available data within a dataspace

Figure 8 Core actors

A *service* actor can be a *business service* with a corresponding business model or an *IT-service*. A (natural) person or organisation are both *legal entities* while services are not.

For handling verifiable claims (statements about a subject), the following generic roles are relevant for dataspace too, because verifiable identities and verifiable claims in general are the cornerstone within a dataspace:

Figure 9 Claim actors

Ref x

The following actors are defined¹² to enable verifiable identities/claims:

- *Issuer*, asserts claims about one or more subjects, creates a verifiable credential (VC) from these claims, and transmits them to a holder;
- *Holder*, possesses one or more verifiable credentials and generates verifiable presentations (VP) from them;
- *Verifier*, relying party or client receiving one or more verifiable credentials, optionally inside a VP for processing;
- *Verifiable data registry*, mediating service to assist the creation and verification of identifiers, keys, and other relevant data, such as verifiable credential schemas, revocation registries, issuer public keys, and so on, which might be required to use verifiable credentials.

IDS Dataspace actors

The IDS-RAM[4] describes four categories of actors: *core participants*, *intermediary*, *software & service providers* and *governance body*.

An exact definition of the core-actors and an elaborate description can be found in IDS-RAM[4] and the DIN-SPEC-27070 [5]. This document only highlights the main aspects relevant for the functional use-case.

Ref 4,5

A *dataspace participant* is defined as a *legal entity* with a unique verifiable identity, authenticated and accepted within a dataspace, who has accepted and is committed to the governance model of that dataspace.

¹² Summary of the definitions stated in Verifiable Credentials Data Model v1.1 [24]

Figure 10 Dataspace actors

Core participants

All core participants are legal entities.

- *Data owner*, creates and has legal control over the data based on data access and usage policies. Can be data provider it self or delegate that role;
- *Data provider*, makes data available (on behalf of data owner) for data consumers and submits metadata for discovery purpose;
- *Data consumer*, receives data from the data provider;
- *Data user*, a data consumer with the legal rights to use data based on data access and data usage policies agreed with the data owner;
- *App provider*, develops DataApps¹³ compliant to the architecture of the dataspace), submits DataApps for certification and distributes them via an App store service.

Intermediary actors

Intermediary actors are trusted¹⁴ *legal entities* who are establishing trust, providing metadata and supporting dataspace functionalities for the *participants*.

¹³ DataApps are software components to provides access to data and data processing capabilities in collaboration with a Security Gateway software component.

¹⁴ Being a trusted participant is a key aspect of realizing “implicit” trust within a dataspace c.q. among the other participants of that dataspace.

Figure 11 IDS intermediary actors

An intermediary actor has created a business model with corresponding *business service(s)* to provide one or more *IT services* to participants.

- *Broker service provider*, stores and manages meta-information about available data;
- *Identity provider*, creates, maintains, manages, monitors, and validates identity information of and for participants;
- *Clearing house*, provides clearing and settlement services for (all) financial and data exchange transactions;
- *App store provider*, provides trusted Data Apps and facilitates publishing and retrieving of Data Apps including corresponding metadata;
- *Vocabulary provider*, manages and offers ontologies, reference data models, or metadata elements being used with the dataspace.

Software and IT-Service providers

Software and *IT-service providers* are IT companies and therefore also legal entities which perform delegated actions and have a technical supporting role within a dataspace in contrast to *intermediate actors* which have a functional supporting role.

The roles are defined as:

- *Software provider*, provides software for implementing the functionality required for the dataspace. In contrast to Data Apps, the software will not be distributed via the App Store service;

- *IT Service provider*¹⁵, provides the deployment of the required infrastructure for participation in a dataspace.

Governance body

The *governance body* is an organisation to facilitate the dataspace with controlling functionality such as certification, evaluation and governance of the dataspace, based on a governance model agreed by the participants of that dataspace.

Figure 12 Governance body actors and relations with operations

The following roles are identified:

- *Certification authority* for authentication of participants and certification of services and software;
- *Evaluation body* verifies with audits if dataspace operations are compliant with the governance model and regulations¹⁶;
- *Dataspace board* represents the dataspace on behalf of the participants and is accountable for compliance with the governance model;
- *Operations* is responsible for daily operations in collaboration with intermediary services and optionally provides a servicedesk to assist new and existing participants.

¹⁵ The name “service provider” used by IDS-RAM[5] is made more specific by using the term “IT-service provider” to distinguish it from a “business service provider”.

¹⁶ The governance model should be compliant with regulations to begin with and periodic checks on regulatory compliancy are required because the world is in motion.

The *certification* and *evaluation authorities* are both part of the *governance body* but can be delegated to external specialized organization capable of providing professional, specialized and independent/objective services. An example of an *evaluation authority* is for instance the *GDPR supervisory authority*. (see below)

The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and corresponding actors are mentioned here for completeness reasons and the definitions are not copied into this document because they are standardized and clearly specified.

Figure 13 GDPR actors

For completeness reasons as well, the OpenDEI[3] also recognises business governance actors as shown below and includes an actor not mentioned yet: the *data marketplace operator* which is a specialized *business service provider* taking care of the required infrastructure and is responsible for marketplace governance by defining terms and conditions, providing support services, and deciding on admission and withdrawal of datasets or participants.

Figure 14 Business governance actors

3. Requirements

A detailed description of the building blocks can be found in the OpenDEI positioning paper[3] but to give the requirements some context in this document, a short description of each building block has been included as a quote, in italic and with reference to the source in the margin on the left side.

3.1 Data models & formats (DF)

Ref 3

“This building block establishes a common format for data model specifications and representation of data in data exchange payloads. Combined with the Data Exchange APIs building block, this ensures full interoperability among participants”.

There are no high level requirements identified yet. The choice of a semantic model such as the DEMETER Agriculture Information Model (AIM)[27] could be a candidate for a high level requirement for data models. The choice of a suitable semantic model as starting point and foundation for API definitions depend on the required flows of information which are currently not determined by the SILLs.

3.2 Data exchange API (DE)

Ref 3

“This building block facilitates the sharing and exchange of data (i.e., data provision and data consumption/use) between dataspace participants”.

The following diagram visualizes the actors and the required data exchange functionality as use-cases.

Figure 15 Data exchange use-cases

Create Connection (C)

Creating a connection means preparing the providing and consuming systems for the exchange of data within the agreed terms and conditions of the dataspace and a mutually agreed access contract c.q. access policies¹⁷.

DE-C01
[4][6] A *participant (data-consumer or data-provider)* can setup/create a connection with another *participant* if both have agreed on a data exchange “access” contract (see section 3.6) and the connection conditions and parameters are compliant to that access contract.

Update Connection (U)

DE-U01
[4][6] A *participant (data-consumer or data-provider)* can change one or more connection parameters while a connection has been established as long as the changes are compliant with the access contract and the dataspace policies. For example: update of an access token or expiration time.

Exchange data (E)

DE-E01
[4][6] A *participant (data-consumer or data-provider)* can exchange data via an established connection with another participant within the policies of the agreed access contract. This implies that contract based policy enforcement is implemented [DP-B01 and DP-B02]

Close connection (T)

Closing or terminating a connection means disabling providing and consuming systems to exchange data.

DE-T01
[4][6] A *participant (data-consumer or data-provider)* can close/terminate a connection with another *participant* according to the rules agreed in the access contract. See also [DP-G07]).

Note The high level requirements for the specification of data to be exchanged are unknown at time of writing this document pending the analysis of the required information flows..

¹⁷ This implies that the access policies are also compliant to the governance legislation rules since the contract must be compliant with them. See section 3.6

3.3 Provenance & Traceability (PT)

Ref 3

"This building block provides the means for tracing and tracking in the process of data provision and data consumption/use. It thereby provides the basis for a number of important functions, from identification of the lineage of data to audit-proof logging of transactions. It also enables implementation of a wide range of tracking use cases at application level, such as tracking of products or material flows in a supply chain".

This functionality is not required for a minimal viable implementation of a dataspace. There are also no requirements identified yet by the SILLs and therefore no use-cases are collected and described. In case the implementation of Data Marketplaces requires provenance & traceability, than this section will be updated.

3.4 Identity management (IM)

Ref 3

"Identity Management (IM) building block allows **identification, authentication, and authorisation¹⁸ (IAA)** of stakeholders operating in a data space. It ensures that organisations, individuals, machines, and other actors are provided with acknowledged identities, and that those identities can be authenticated and verified, including additional information provisioning, to be used by authorisation mechanisms to enable access and usage control".

The following diagram visualizes the actors and the required identification & authentication functionality as use-cases.

Figure 16 Identification and authentication use-cases

¹⁸ Authorisation will be described in section 3.6 in combination with Access Control & Usage policies because both functional aspects are entangled.

Register (R)

- IM-R01 [4][6] An *outsider* can request a membership to a dataspace by providing credentials or in general claims. After a successful authentication of the claims, the outsider can become a *participant* of the dataspace if the *outsider* is compliant with the terms and conditions for membership to be checked by an *identity provider*. Otherwise the request will be refused and the outsider becomes a *refused-outsider*¹⁹.
- IM-R02 [4] An *Identity provider* can accept or reject a registration request based on terms and conditions for membership specified in a governance model. An accepted registration results in an *unique verifiable and trusted identity* linked to a specific *participant* with corresponding verifiable claims.
- IM-G01 [6] The governance model must describe terms and conditions for membership including how claims will be verified.
- IM-R03 [4] An *Identity provider* stores the identity and claims of *participants* and *refused-outsiders* according to terms and conditions defined in a governance model.
- IM-G02 [6] The governance model must describe rules for storing and removing information about *(ex-)participants* and *refused-outsiders*.

Authenticate (A)

- IM-A01 [4] An *Identity provider* is able to request verification of claims as part of the registration or verification process. The *Identity provider* can but is not obliged to delegate this task to a *Certification Authority*.
- IM-A02 [4] An *Identity provider* accepts or rejects an authorisation request based on terms and conditions specified in a governance model.
- IM-G03 [6] The governance model must describe terms and conditions for accepting and rejecting authentication requests.

Verify (V)

- IM-V01 [4] A *participant* is able to verify if another participant has a valid and known identification within the dataspace.

¹⁹ The role of *refused-outsider* is relevant in case information from the registration or authentication process is stored as part of a blacklist or to optimize the registration process as part of another attempt to register by a *refused-outsider*. If no information is kept, then the actor type *refused-outsider* is obsolete.

IM-V02 [4] A *participant* is able to verify if claims of another participant are valid based on a valid identification.

IM-V03 [4] An *Identity provider* is able to verify identities and claims for participants.

IM-G04 [4] The governance model must describe the basic set of meta-information related to a participant being available for all participants of the dataspace.

Terminate (T)

IM-T01 [6] A *participant* requests via the Identity provider to end the participants membership to the dataspace.

IM-G05 [6] Governance model describes rules for participants leaving the dataspace. For example, outstanding obligations to other participants and/or supporting actors such as service providers, need to be fulfilled first. Data consumers might require a minimal period to enable them to switch to another data provider or to adapt their processes.

IM-T02 [4] The *Governance body* authorises the *identity provider* to remove a *participant* after the Governance body has checked if the *participant* has fulfilled its obligations as specified in the governance model. See [IM-G05].

Clean up (C)

IM-C01 [IM-T02] An *Identity provider* removes the information about a leaving participant stored in the Identity management services, according to the terms and conditions defined in the governance model.

IM-G06 [6] The governance model describes terms and conditions for removing information about a participant depending on regulations in terms of what and how long information needs to be available for legal purposes.

Evaluate (E)

IM-E01 [4] An *Identity provider* verifies the agreed governance rules (terms and conditions) and informs the Governance body in case of deviations.

IM-G07 [IM-E01] The *Governance body* requests information about evaluations of the operational process, procedures and deviations as agreed in governance model.

IM-G08 [6] The governance model describes the evaluation of *Identity providers* and in particular which regulations are applicable.

3.5 Trusted exchange (TE)

Ref 3 *“This building block facilitates trusted data exchange among participants, reassuring participants in a data exchange transaction that other participants really are who they claim to be and that they comply with defined rules/agreements. This can be achieved by organisational measures (e.g. certification or verified credentials) or technical measures (e.g. remote attestation)”.*

Issuing and verification of credentials are described as part of Identity Management with use-cases Register[IM-Rxx] and Verify[IM-Vxx]. This section describes the high level requirements for certification of participants and software components²⁰. The certification process for an IDS compliant dataspace regarding participants and core (software) components are described in Designing Data Spaces section 9.3 [xx] in particular. The use of an evaluation facility is most likely required but omitted here.

Figure 17 Certificate use-cases

Apply to certification (A)

TE-A01 [4] A *participant* also known as the applicant, can request a certification for itself or a core software component. Certification of IT-services is foreseen but currently still subject for research and development. As result the applicant receives a certificate as proof or a rejection with motivation and suggestions for improvements.

²⁰ Certification of services is also identified within Gaia-X and is currently under research and development. IT-services are not only depending on how well software components implement the agreed interfaces, the quality of the service is also depending on the quality and reliability of the underlying processes and data it provides.

TE-A02 [4] An *Evaluation body* as part of the *Governance body* of a dataspace can accept or deny a certification request based on terms and conditions defined in the governance model.

TE-G01 WP2 The governance model must describe terms and conditions for certification of participants and software components including a description of the certification process.

Register certification (R)

TE-R01 [4] An *Evaluation body* can store and remove (meta) information about certification requests including the results of the certification process, based on terms and conditions defined in the governance model.

TE-G02 WP2 The governance model must describe what (meta) information should be stored including terms and conditions for storing and removing (meta) information in a certification register. This includes the duration for which certificates are valid and the expiration date per certificate.

Verify a certification (V)

TE-V01 [4] A *participant, IT-service or a software component*, can verify if a given certification for a specific participant or core software component is valid, not expired or not revoked.

TE-V02 [4] An *Evaluation body* can handle a certification verification request with use of a certification registry and based on terms and conditions defined in the governance model including what (meta) information shall be returned.

TE-G03 WP2 The governance model must describe terms and conditions for the response of certification verification request including what (meta) information shall be returned.

3.6 Access & Usage control/policies (AU)

Ref 3 *"The Access and Usage Control/Policies building block guarantees enforcement of data access and usage policies defined as part of the terms and conditions established when data resources or services are published (see 'Publication and Services Marketplace' building block below) or negotiated between providers and consumers. A data provider typically implements data access control mechanisms to prevent misuse of resources, while data usage control mechanisms are typically implemented on the data consumer side to prevent misuse of data. In complex data value chains, both mechanisms are*

combined by prosumers. Access control and usage control rely on identification and authentication”.

The following diagram visualizes the roles/actors and authorization activities based on *access and usage policies* specified in an *access contract* between a data provider and a data consumer. The use of access policies is not mandatory but a transparent mechanism to make access decisions based on verified and trusted identities.

Figure 18 Data access and data usage policies use-cases

Setup access policies (S)

- AU-S01 [4] A *data provider* can define or change access and usage policies in a contract to describe which data can be accessed under specific conditions.
A contract for data access can be for a specific data consumer, for a group or being applicable for all data consumers within the dataspace .

- AU-S02 [4] A *data consumer* can read the proposed access and usage policies, made available by a data provider.

Negotiate contract (N)

- AU-N01 [4] A *data provider* proposes a new or changed contract to a *data consumer*. A *data consumer* can accept, reject or request changes to a contract.

Contract based access (B)

- AU-B01 [4] A *data provider* can grant and revoke access to data as specified in the contract.

AU-G01
WP2 A governance model might include general conditions when data access can be revoked by a data provider.

AU-B02
[4] A *data consumer* can access/request data from a data provider according to the policies as specified in the contract.

Withdraw contract (T)

AU-T01
[6] Withdrawal of an access contract means that both the *data provider* and the *data consumer* agree not to exchange data any more. The purposes of this withdrawal process is to give both the data consumer as well as the data provider the opportunity to make preparations to services and processes. (This in contrast to the option for the data provider to revoke access as a single sided decision)

3.7 Metadata & Discovery services (MD)

Ref 3 *"This building block incorporates publishing and discovery mechanisms for data resources and services, making use of common descriptions of resources, services, and participants. Such descriptions can be both domain-agnostic and domain-specific. They should be enabled by semantic-web technologies and include linked-data principles."*

Figure 19 Discovery use-cases

Describe (D)

MD-D01
[4] A *participant* can create common description c.q. meta-information about data, software component or services it can provide, based on a within the dataspace accepted semantic model.

MD-G01
WP2 The governance model must describe the semantic model for describing (meta) information to be published via a *broker*.

MD-D02 [4] A *Vocabulary provider* can provide access to semantic models to be used for describing data, software component and services.

Publish (P)

MD-P01 [4] A *participant* can publish a new or adaptation of a description if it complies with the agreed semantic model.

MD-P02 [4] The *broker* will handle publish, search and revoke requests but only from verified and valid *participants*²¹.

MD-P03 [4] The *broker* can validate descriptions against an agreed semantic model. Invalid descriptions will be rejected.

MD-P04 [4] The *broker* can store a valid description from a valid participant in a metadata register²².

Search (S)

MD-S01 [4] A *participant* can search for descriptions with use of predefined set of information elements.

MD-S02 [4] The *broker* can facilitate a description search request with use of the metadata register.

Revoke (R)

MD-R01 [4] A *participant* can revoke its own descriptions.

MD-R02 [4] A *broker* can revoke descriptions based on terms and conditions specified by the governance model.

MD-G02 [4] The governance model must describe the terms and conditions for revoking description by a *broker*.

²¹ Participants are by definition “verifiable & valid”. All (intermediary) IT-services should verify if they are dealing with valid participants. It is stated here explicitly because the broker is a cornerstone of a dataspace and requires implicit trust so that all participants can rely on the information provided the broker.

²² In case of federated brokers the metadata register will also be federated.

3.8 Publication & Marketplace services (PM)

Ref 3 *“This building block provides the basis for accounting access to and/or usage of data by different users. This in turn is supportive of important functions for clearing, payment, and billing (including data-sharing transactions without involvement of data marketplaces).*

A data marketplace can be cross-domain or domain-specific (i.e. dealing with data of interest to specific use cases and industries). Their main duty is to make data easily discoverable (based on a set of standardised data models) and to provide transparent tracking of all data-related transactions (from who used what data at what point in time to revenues generated from sharing data)”.

Figure 20 Data marketplace use-cases

Broker (B)

PM-B01 [4] A *data marketplace* is a specialized type of a *broker* to offer publication functionality. From a functional and technical dataspace point of view, a data marketplace is a specialised version of a broker. Therefore all requirements for “Metadata and Discovery” services also apply for a *data marketplace*.

From a business point of view, a *data market place* offers additional functionality to provide transparent tracking of all data-related transactions.

Setup agreements (A)

PM-A01 [4] *Participants* (data/service providers and consumers) can negotiate about the terms and conditions for access and usage of a business service.

PM-A02 [4] A *data marketplace* facilitates the negotiation among *participants* or more precise between providers and consumers. The result is an agreement.

Perform transactions (T)

PM-T01 [4] *Participants* can perform data-related transactions (access and usage of a business service) based on mutually agreed terms and conditions.

PM-T02 [4] A *data marketplace* facilitates the data-related transaction process as a trusted intermediary IT-service by keeping track of all data-related transactions (logging). The result might be sent to a *Clearinghouse*.

Enable accounting (D)

PM-D01 [4] A *participant* can request meta-information about provided or consumed data-related transactions which were handled by the *data marketplace* (internally) or being stored (externally) in *Clearinghouse*²³.

PM-D02 [4] A *data marketplace* can provide meta-information about data-related transactions based on internally stored data and/or with use of an external *Clearinghouse*.

Specify governance (S)

PM-S01 [3] A *data marketplace operator*²⁴ shall define the terms and conditions for marketplace governance including rules for admission and withdrawal of datasets or participants. This also includes a description of the meta-information to be stored and the corresponding semantic model to be used. The marketplace governance must be compliant with the governance model of the dataspace.

PM-S02 [3] A *data marketplace operator* shall put mechanisms in place to ensure compliance with data usage policies (e.g. with regard to the time and count the data was used, or fields of application in which certain data cannot be used).

²³ A *Clearinghouse* can be used by multiple data marketplaces and data-related transactions can also take place without a *data marketplace*.

²⁴ A *data marketplace operator* is a specialized business service provider taking care of the required infrastructure and is responsible for marketplace governance by defining terms and conditions, providing support services, and deciding on admission and withdrawal of datasets or participants.

3.9 Data usage accounting (DU)

Ref 3 *"To support the offering of data resources and services under defined terms and conditions, marketplaces must be established. This building block supports publication of these offerings, management of processes linked to the creation and monitoring of smart contracts²⁵ (which clearly describe the rights and obligations for data and service usage), and access to data and services."*

Note: This functionality is identified as not required for the ZeroW project and therefore no use-cases are collected and described. In case the SILLs require data usage accounting and the creation and monitoring of smart contracts in particular, than this section will be update.

The implementation of "smart contracts" is not within the scope of the ZeroW project, unless the outcome of further analysis of the business requirements from the SILLs might conclude otherwise. For now it is left out to simplify the first step towards the implementation of a OFLW dataspace.

3.10 Business agreements (BU)

Ref 3 *"As data is the most important factor of a data-driven business, it is crucial to use quality data in terms of accuracy, reliability, resolution, availability, etc. Responsibility to ensure that data is of the quality required and agreed upon starts with the Data Owner and then goes over to each party involved in the data value chain. An important aspect of business relationships is compliance with the rules specifying how data can be used by participants and third parties."*

BU-G01 [3] The governance model must describe the business model for all intermediary dataspace services including a strategy to finance operations.

BU-G02 [3] The governance model must describe how to preserve Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) and the ownership and confidentiality of data in general as a common foundation for multi-lateral contracts and agreements.

BU-G03 [3] The governance model must describe a Domain Data Standard which represents the semantic model for data sharing in a specific sector or domain. To achieve specific goals, multiple such standards can be used in combination.

BU-G04 [3] The governance model must describe a strategy and policy regarding the growth of the dataspace and in particular the transition from small-scale to larger scales.

²⁵ Smart contracts for Marketplaces require more research and development to achieve automatic handling the rights and obligations for data and service usage, including access to data and services according to the terms of an agreement.

3.11 Operational agreements (OP)

- Ref 3 *“From the perspective of a Data Provider and/or Data Owner, data control capabilities for ensuring data sovereignty²⁶, trust and security in a data space are necessary to prevent the misuse of data shared and exchanged. To ensure data sovereignty in data sharing and exchange, both organisational and operational agreements must be in place. While such agreements support and enable data usage policies, they also bring trust into the whole data ecosystem, as they function as a trust anchor connecting the physical and the digital world. Interoperability of the system as a whole relies on agreements that ensure interoperability between all participants.”*
- OP-G01 [3] The governance model must describe the operational model for managing all intermediary dataspace services.
- OP-G02 [3] The governance model must describe operational Service Level Agreements (SLA) for intermediary services to ensure an uninterrupted and reliable data value chain.
- OP-G03 [3] The governance model must describe the operational model for supporting intermediary dataspace services such as a service desk and change management.
- OP-G04 [3] The governance model must describe an accounting scheme: This artifact details the accounting practices and reports that should be produced as part of the operation of the data space and in line with the underlying business models. It specifies the parameters that should be logged and reported for every business actor and transaction of the data space
- OP-G05 [3] The governance model must describe a billing/charging scheme: Leveraging accounting data and reports, data spaces provide the means for billing of services and transactions. In this context, specification of the billing/charging scheme is important. This artifact specifies how billing/charging is to be performed.
- OP-G06 [3] In case of smart contracts²⁷ are used, the governance model must describe a protocol for implementation of agreements between two or more parties (mainly the *Data Provider* and the *Data Consumer*).

²⁶ Data sovereignty is a natural person’s or corporate entity’s capability of being entirely self-determined with regard to its data. This means, data sovereignty allows a legal person to exclusively decide about the usage of its data as an economic asset. In practice, it allows organisations and individuals to stay in control over the terms and conditions under which their data is made available to others, and how it may be used and processed by them. Source [3]

²⁷ Smart contracts are specifying transaction protocols that automate the execution of actions required for provision of a service by one or more parties. Source [3]

OP-G07 [3] The governance model might describe a method to estimate the value of data shared by *participants* in the data space.

3.12 Organisational agreements (OR)

Ref 3 The organisational agreements describe the formation and responsibilities of the governance body of a dataspace, common standards, agreements and rules applicable for all participants.

OR-G01 [3] The governance model must describe the organisational formation such as a *Dataspace Board*²⁸, *Certification* and *Evaluation Authorities*, *Intermediary Service Providers* and *Dataspace Operations*.

OR-G02 [3] The governance model must describe unique and trusted identifiers to enable reliable identification of entities (including things) across domain specific or country specific identification schemes.

OR-G03 [3] The governance model must describe the authorisation process and register to unambiguously identify and verify *participants*. These registries need to be established in accordance with operational agreements (i.e. policies).

OR-G04 [3] The governance model must describe the terms and conditions for (intermediary) trusted parties including a process description to set-up, maintain and to end the relation with a trusted party.

OR-G05 [3] The governance model must describe overarching cooperation agreements regarding functional, technical, operational and legal aspects which all *participants* need to agree on.

OR-G06 [3] The governance model must describe a continuity model for the management of changes, versions, and releases for standards and agreements. This includes procedures for decision-making and conflict resolution.

OR-G07 [3] The governance model must describe regulations²⁹ to guide or prescribe the conduct of the *participants*.

²⁸ Dataspace Boards provide governance for data spaces in terms of decision-making, guidance, steering, and conflict resolution.

²⁹ Laws, administrative rules or regulations issued by an organisation

3.13 Federation of services (FD)

Ref 1 In the context of the ZeroW project, federated data-services are about sharing information between decentralised services where the information can be requested at one service while the data itself can be stored³⁰ distributed across one or more other federating services.

The previous requirements in this chapter are applicable for a single dataspace and need to be extended with the following use-cases to facilitate federation of services. The uses-cases for federated services are also applicable for a federated broker, federated marketplace and a federated catalogue.

Figure 21 Federation use-cases

Describe & Discovery (D)

To enable collaboration between federated services the first step is to define the governance model of such service and to find compliant services to connect with. Therefore the use-case for Metadata and Discovery as defined in section 3.7 are applicable for federated services. This includes the use-case “describe” as visualised in the figure above.

FD-D01 [4] A *federated service* is a verifiable and trusted *IT-service* of a dataspace. This doesn't mean that a valid *participant* in one dataspace is automatically valid³¹ in another dataspace.

³⁰ Decentralisation of data storage and IT-services in general is a mitigating measurement to increase more control to participants and reduce a dominating influence by a single participant. In ultimo, keeping the data at the source will also make it easier to implement more control over the data: so called data-sovereignty.

³¹ depends on the governance model of a dataspace.

FD-D02 [4] A *federated service operator* describes in a governance model the terms and conditions for connecting with other federated services and “external” participants.

FD-D03 [4] A *Federated service operator* describes in a governance model which (meta)-information they can provide and the terms and conditions for sharing them.

FD-D04 [4] A *Federated service operator* describes in a governance model the mechanism(s) how to exchange and to store information.

FD-D05 WP2 The governance model of a *federated service* must be compliant with the governance model of the dataspace of that service.

FD-G01 WP2 The governance model must describe the policy about the use of federated services within a dataspace and must address at least the topics about Identity Management and Trusted Exchange to ensure that only verifiable and valid participants can use the dataspace. The Business, Operational and Organisational governance aspects for federated services requires also attention for a practical implementation. This involves agreements about (sharing) costs for operations and a procedure for change management in general and the changes to interfaces in particular. Free for all and only using stable and standardized API's seems the most simple solution here but is unfortunately not the current reality.

Connect (C)

FD-C01 [4] A *federated service* can connect to other *federated services* if this is in consent with the *governance bodies* of the involved dataspaces. This implies also compliancy with the governance models of the involved dataspaces. Use of one common governance model would reduce the complexity but is not a requirement.

Share (S)

FD-S01 [4] A *federated service* can exchange (meta)-information with other connected *federated services* within the terms and conditions of the mutually agreed governance models.

Withdrawal (W)

FD-W01 [4] A *federated service* can end the collaboration with one or more other *federated services* based on terms and conditions specified by the governance model.

FD-W02 [4] The governance model of *federated services* must specify the terms and conditions for ending the collaboration with another federated service.

4. Conclusions

4.1 State of the Art analysis

A desk research of dataspace related projects and initiatives has resulted in a brief highlevel overview of functional requirements.

The new European Interoperability Framework[2], the OpenDEI Positioning Paper[3], the IDS-Reference Architecture Model[4] and corresponding IDS standard DIN-27070[5] offer a good starting point (dataspace foundation) for designing a data sharing solution as a OFLW dataspace for the ZeroW project.

Inspired by the work of the Digital Innovation HUB – SmartAgriHUB, a Solution Maturity Model has been defined in section 2.3 of this document to analyse the availability of solutions to implement the required functional aspects (building blocks) as identified by the OpenDEI Positioning paper[3].

A semantical foundation for self-description is expected from Gaia-X medio 2022 which can contribute to design and implementation of a Federated catalogue which is a technical research objective within the ZeroW project.

The following overview presents the availability of solutions to implement the functional building blocks to be taken in account for setting up a dataspace.

Figure 22 Available solutions for a OFLW dataspace

Six building blocks (orange hexagons) require further research and development to be performed within the ZeroW project. There are solutions (green hexagons) available for four building blocks. However, these solutions still need to be deployed c.q. installed and configured as part of the realization of a OFLW dataspace. For a minimum viable implementation, the building blocks for Provenance & Traceability and Data Usage Accounting are not required (grey hexagons).

The following table describes which building-block have suitable solutions (green) and which building blocks require more research and development (orange).

Building block	SML ³²	Comments
<i>Data interoperability</i>		
Data models & formats	Low	A Vocabulary hub can be used to define and agree upon the required data models and corresponding exchange of information. An existing semantic model for Agriculture such as AIM is recommended.
Data Exchange API	Low	A software framework based on OpenAPI is available but implementation is depending on required <i>data models & formats</i> to define messages and to create community API's.
Provenance & traceability	Ad-hoc	Not required for a minimal viable implementation.
<i>Data sovereignty</i>		
Identity management	Intermediate	Different multiple identities for the same participant needs to be resolved which requires additional development effort. Use of eIDAS, SSI or DID needs to be decided.
Trusted Exchange	Intermediate	Configuration depends on <i>Operational agreements</i> and the implementation of a Governance model in general.
Access & usage control/policies	Intermediate	Development of "easy-to-use" GUI's for the configuration of access policies by WP2 task 2.3 is recommended.
<i>Data value creation</i>		
Metadata & discovery services	Intermediate	Development of a federated catalogue (research objective) can be based on existing implementation of a federated broker.
Publication & Marketplace services	Ad-hoc	Development of a federated catalogue (research objective) in WP2 task T2.4 can be based on existing implementation of a federated broker. Marketplace services require additional SILL related development of the applications by WP3 task 3.x and the required <i>data models</i> .
Data usage accounting	Ad-hoc	Not required for a minimal viable implementation.
<i>Dataspace governance</i>		
Business agreements	Low	Further development is part of WP2 task 2.2
Operational agreements	Low	Ditto, plus IDS Rule book [x] has been recently published and contains practical guidelines for a ZeroW implementation.
Organizational agreements	Low	Ditto.

Table 4 Solutions maturity inventory for building blocks

³² SML = Solution maturity level, see section 2.3

4.2 Requirements

This document provides a first attempt to create a complete and comprehensive overview of actors and the high level functional requirements for a dataspace based on the collective results of previous dataspace related initiatives and projects. Such overview for all OpenDEI building blocks[3] in terms of actors and use-cases (scenario's) was not available until now.

More technical and detailed requirements can already be found in the IDS standard described in DIN-27070[5] which will be completed with requirements not covered by the IDS standard in the follow-up document: D2.2 – Reference with specification for connectors.

The high-level requirements and the governance requirements in particular can be used for the implementation of OFLW dataspace and the development of collaborative business and governance models for data sharing in OFLW.

4.3 Recommendations

The overview of actors and their use-cases require peer-reviews from other initiatives such as IDSA. Presenting them at the IDS-plugfest³³ is a good starting point. This recommendation implies that an update of this document and in particular section 2.4 and chapter 3 is expected after receiving external feedback.

The use of a Vocabulary hub will enable the creation of Community API's where involved participants of a dataspace can design and agree upon the required data models and formats. Community based tooling will reduce tremendously the time required to establish a commonly agreed semantic model and formats, and will result in the same understanding and interpretation of the exchange data.

Additional effort to create easy-to-use Graphical User Interfaces for the configuration/specification of data access policies (rules) will also reduce the barrier to participate in a OFLW dataspace. This can be part of task 2.3 in WP2.

Active collaboration with DSBA (IDSA, Gaia-X and FIWARE) is recommended to pursue a common approach and standards for the development of a Federated Catalogue. Also further development within these initiatives might be helpful for ZeroW and vice versa. The joined effort of IDSA, NTT Communications, Omron, Fraunhofer Institute, Sovity and TNO has recently (April/May 2022) resulted in a first of its kind federation of dataspace. Such collaboration is an example of achieving technical innovation faster and with broad commitment.

³³ The IDSA Plugfest[32] is held quarterly in the IDS Lab at the Fraunhofer Institute for Software and Systems Engineering ISST in Dortmund. It is geared towards the consolidation of and technical connection between the existing IDS core components. Implementing an initial MVP-IDS ecosystem is the overriding objective.

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